

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Diethanolamine by Alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III)

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The kinetics of the oxidation of diethanolamine by hexacyanoferrate (III) in alkaline medium has been studied. The reaction has been found to have first order dependence both in diethanolamine and hexacyanoferrate (III). The oxidation has been found to depend upon OH^- concentration. The effect of addition of salts like sodium chloride, potassium sulphate and sodium acetate is slightly positive, while the effect of hexacyanoferrate (II) ion is negligible. A mechanism involving the formation of an intermediate amine anion has been proposed.

POTASSIUM hexacyanoferrate (III) falls into the class of oxidising agents comprising ceric sulphate, ammoniacal silver nitrate and Fehling's solution, in all of which the oxidizing species is a complex electron abstracting ion.

There are innumerable instances where alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) has been utilized with considerable success though its capacity was not originally apparent¹.

The kinetics of the oxidation of a number of organic compounds, by hexacyanoferrate (III) has been studied by many workers²⁻⁹. However, the kinetics of the oxidation of amino alcohols by this oxidant has not received any attention so far, though their oxidation has been investigated by other oxidising agents^{10,11}.

In the present communication, the kinetics of the oxidation of diethanolamine by hexacyanoferrate (III) has been investigated.

Experimental

Aqueous potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) was prepared from an Analar BDH sample and the concentration was checked by iodometry¹². All other chemicals used were also A.R. BDH of extra pure quality and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. In every case glass vessels of pyrex or of Jena Gerat Glass were used. The reaction vessels were coated with black Japan to exclude photochemical effects.

The requisite amounts of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) and sodium hydroxide solutions of desired concentrations were placed in a reaction flask. The mixture ($\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and NaOH solutions) and amine solution of desired concentration

were separately kept in a thermostated bath maintained at the desired temperature within the range of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The reaction was started by adding the requisite volume of amine solution to the mixture. The kinetics of the reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed hexacyanoferrate (III) iodometrically (loc. cit.). Owing to high initial concentration of the alkali ($[\text{OH}^-] = 0.1M$), the pH remained constant during the progress of the reaction.

Results

To determine the moles of hexacyanoferrate (III) consumed per mole of the amine, a known amount of diethanolamine was mixed with 10 to 15 times its molar concentration of alkaline potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) at $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.1M$ and the mixture was left for 3 days at room temperature, when the reaction was complete. The unconsumed oxidant was determined. It was found that the reaction can be represented by the stoichiometric equation

The product formaldehyde was confirmed by the chromotropic acid reaction test¹³. Smith and Willeford¹⁴ have also reported the formation of formaldehyde in the periodate oxidation of diethanolamine.

A number of runs having equimolar concentrations of the amine and hexacyanoferrate (III) were studied, in alkaline medium ($[\text{OH}^-] = 0.1M$), at different temperatures. For each run a plot of $x/a-x$ against time was found to be a straight line (Fig. 1) for nearly 60% of the reaction. Second order constants, at different temperatures, were calculated both from the equation,

$$k_2 = \frac{x}{a(a-x)t}$$

Fig. 1. [Diethanolamine] = [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 2 × 10⁻³M, [NaOH] = 1 × 10⁻¹M

and the slope of the curves (Fig. 1). The results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Diethanolamine Fe(CN)₆³⁻ = 2.0 × 10⁻³M, OH⁻ = 1.0 × 10⁻¹M

Temp.	pH = 13			
	30°	35°	45°	40°
K ₂ L mol ⁻¹ min. ⁻¹	9.635	12.635	15.50	17.00

The total order is found to be two. All subsequent investigations were also carried out with different concentrations of the amine, while keeping other parameters constant. The initial rate increases, though not linearly, with the increase in the concentration of the amine. The initial rate vs. [diethanolamine]^{0.8} plot is a straight line passing through the origin (Fig. 2). This shows that the order with respect to the amine is 0.8 which may be taken nearly to be unity. Since the total order of the

Fig. 2. [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 2 × 10⁻³M, [NaOH] = 1 × 10⁻¹M Temp. = 40°.

reaction is two and the order in the amine is unity, the order with respect to hexacyanoferrate (III) is, obviously, unity. Further it was also observed that an increase in the initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate (III) decreased the rate (Table 2). Such a behaviour has also been observed by Bohning and

Weiss (loc. cit.) in the oxidation of 3-mercaptopropionic acid using the same oxidant. This is, probably, due to the steady state concentration of some intermediate product which becomes significant at higher concentration of hexacyanoferrate (III). This intermediate product may also liberate iodine when analysing for hexacyanoferrate (III), thus giving higher values for the oxidant and consequently low value of the rate.

The rate of the reaction has been found to depend upon OH⁻ concentration. At lower concentration of NaOH, the plot between the initial rate and [NaOH] is linear passing through the origin (Fig. 3a), confirming the possibility of the reaction only in the alkaline medium, but at higher concentrations, the initial rate varies as the square root of initial [NaOH] (Fig. 3b).

Fig. 3a. [Diethanolamine] = 3 × 10⁻³M, [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 2 × 10⁻³M Temp. = 40°.

A plot of log *k*₂ and 1/*T* gave a straight line (Fig. 4). From the graph, Arrhenius parameters were evaluated and the values found are Δ*H* = 9.0 Kcal/mole, and Δ*S* = -53.5 e.u.

Fig. 3b. [Diethanolamine] = 3 × 10⁻³M, [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 2 × 10⁻³M Temp. = 40°.

TABLE 2

[Diethanolamine] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[OH^-] = 1 \times 10^{-1} M$,
Temp. 40° .

Conc. of $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ in moles/ $L \times 10^3$	Initial rate $\times 10^5$ in moles/ L of $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$
1.0	4.43
2.0	4.13
4.0	3.30
6.0	2.89
8.0	2.08
10.0	1.69

Fig. 4. [Diethanolamine] = $[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} M$,
[NaOH] = $1 \times 10^{-1} M$

Addition of salts like sodium chloride, potassium sulphate, sodium acetate showed a slight accelerating effect on the reaction rate, while potassium ferrocyanide showed a negligible effect.

The reaction was also studied by adding different number of glass beads in the reaction mixture and it was found that surface/volume ratio plays no role in the reaction.

Nitrogen gas has no effect on the reaction rate, oxygen has a slight accelerating effect. But when CO_2 is passed through the reaction mixture, the reaction rate is very much retarded. The retarding effect of CO_2 may be due to the interaction of CO_2 and an electron in the presence of reducing substance¹⁵ thus forming CO_2^- radical ($CO_2 + e \rightarrow CO_2^-$)

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left[\text{NH} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}^- \\ \diagdown \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array} \right] = k_1 \left[\text{NH} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \\ \diagdown \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array} \right] [\text{OH}^-] - k_{-1} \left[\text{NH} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}^- \\ \diagdown \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array} \right] - k_2 \left[\text{NH} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}^- \\ \diagdown \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array} \right] [Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 0 \quad \dots (iv)$$

$$\text{or} \left[\text{NH} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}^- \\ \diagdown \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array} \right] = \frac{k_1 \left[\text{NH} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \\ \diagdown \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array} \right] [\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-1} + k_2 [Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]} \quad \dots (v)$$

and thus the availability of electron is reduced for the reduction of $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ ions ($Fe(CN)_6^{3-} + e \rightarrow Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$).

The conductivity of the system does not change during the course of the reaction.

The tests for the existence of free radical in the system were negative and hence the possibility of a mechanism, based on free radical, is ruled out.

Discussion

The alkali dependence of the oxidation process involved clearly indicates the oxidation of diethanolamine takes place through an intermediate anion of the reducing substrate formed with hydroxyl ions. In accordance with this view, it has been shown by Waters *et al.*³, that substances like benzaldehyde, which can not enolize or do not form an intermediate anion, are not oxidised by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III), whereas substances like acetone and propanol, which exist in the enolic form, are easily oxidizable. Thus, taking into consideration the kinetic data obtained, the following scheme for the oxidation of diethanolamine is proposed on the basis of the mechanism given by Speakman and Waters³ for the oxidation of carbonyl compounds by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III).

The first step (i) involves the formation of an intermediate anion of the substrate which is essentially reversible in nature.

The step (ii) may be fast or slow depending upon the stability of the intermediate anion obtained in step (i). Step (iii) is relatively fast and gives the products of the reaction. In view of the stoichiometry step (iii) can not form the final products of the reaction, and it seems likely that it generates intermediate products which react further in a sequence of reactions faster than steps (i) to (iii).

Under the steady state condition, the rates of formation and destruction of the intermediate anion must be equal. Hence

Also the loss of hexacyanoferrate (III) may be represented as

According to the above derived rate law, if the rate determining step is (ii), then k_{-1} will become much larger than k_2 and the rate law will approximately reduce to

At constant $[\text{OH}^-]$ ion concentration the above equation can be written as

Here k is the experimentally determined second order rate constant. The kinetic data obtained agree with the derived rate law equation and the mechanism proposed.

According to the proposed mechanism, the rate determining step involves interaction of two negatively charged ions or between negatively charged ion and a polar molecule and thus should correspond to a negative entropy change. This has been found to be true from the experimental data recorded.

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